

TAX ENFORCEMENT MEASURES AND REVENUE OPTIMIZATION OF STATES' INTERNAL REVENUE SERVICE IN NIGERIA

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<p>Keyword: Tax Enforcement Measures, Revenue optimization, States' internal Revenue Service.</p>	<p>Abstract: This study examined tax enforcement measures and revenue optimization in States' internal Revenue Service in Nigeria. The research adopted descriptive survey research design. The population for this study was five hundred and seventy-six senior staff across the State internal Revenue Service in Nigeria and a sample size of two hundred and thirty-six senior staff of State internal Revenue Service in Nigeria. The study used questionnaire instrument, and data were analyzed in the Statistical Package for Social Sciences. The research questions were analyzed using mean and standard deviation and hypotheses were tested using Simple bivariate regression analysis at a significance level of 0.05. The results of the findings showed that there is a positive significant relationship between litigation and measures of revenue optimization in Nigerian States. It was further revealed that there was a strong positive significant relationship between power of distraint and the measures of revenue optimization in Nigerian States. Furthermore, the study also revealed a strong positive significant relationship between search and seizure and the measures of revenue optimization in Nigerian States. Therefore, the study concludes that there is a strong positive relationship between tax enforcement measures and revenue optimization. The study recommends that litigation support should be adopted by State internal Revenue Service in Nigeria as it will enhance the payment of tax by the taxpayers. Tax penalty should be stiff enough to serve as deterrent to would-be tax defaulters; also, power of distraint should be encouraged. Search and Seizure is appropriate when a crime is suspected and therefore will enhance revenue optimization if adopted. Judicious use of taxpayer's money should be made and be seen to have been properly utilized. This will encourage taxpayers to continue to pay taxes.</p>
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INTRODUCTION

Today Nigeria is indeed in need of effective and efficient tax system in order to generate enough revenue that will finance economic growth and development. There is the urgent need in the

country to evolve new approach for handling various tax issues dealing with both compliance and planning work (Samuel, 2014). The use of Tax in National development is increasing, and further introduction of new technology will

Essiet Victor Eniema

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ensure its continued growth and influence in stimulating economic growth. All over the world, nations strive for progress development and continuous improvement in the welfare of their citizens. Developed nations are known for their ability in providing for present generations of their citizens, without jeopardizing the future of coming generations take certain decisions to safeguard their future.

Tax has been defined variously by many authors. One of such definitions takes tax to be “a compulsory payment levied on the citizens by the government for the purpose of achieving its goals”. Its compulsory nature suggests that citizens should comply with payment of tax. The citizenry however may do this voluntarily or it may be through coercion, depending on how the taxpayers perceive the tax system and administration in general (Akintoye & Tashie, 2013). These levies are made on personal Income such as salaries, business profits, interests, dividends, discount and royalties. It is also levied against company profits, petroleum profits, Capital gains, and capital transfer Tax through the capital Transfer decree was abrogated effective from January 1, 1996.

The Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary defines ‘tax’ as: “Money that has to be paid to the government so that it can pay for public services” Black Law Dictionary defines tax as: “Monetary charge imposed by the Government on persons, entities or property, levied to yield public revenue”.

Thomas Cooley defines taxes as: “Enforced

proportional contributions from persons and property, levied by the State, by virtue of its sovereignty, for the support of government and for all public needs”. The National Tax Policy defines as: “a financial charge or levy imposed upon-an individual or legal entity of the State; it is a pecuniary burden laid upon individuals or property to support government expenditure”. It goes on to say that “tax is not a voluntary payment or donation, but an enforced/compulsory contribution, enacted pursuant to legislative authority and is any contribution imposed by the government, whether under the name of duty, custom, excise, levy or other name (Akintoye, & Tashie, 2013).

The need for the government to provide social amenities, embark on developmental projects that would improve the living standards of the citizenry as well as meet its overhead or recurrent expenses necessitate intensified revenue generation efforts both internally and externally (Oladele, Uduma & Aderemi, 2003). Popoola (2009) opined that one of the major sources therefore, to generate revenue is by levying the taxes on the tax object which could be individuals or corporate entities. The subject of taxation has received considerable intellectual and theoretical attention in developed nations (Ayodele, 2006).

Tax plays a very paramount role within the concept of generating revenue for the government while enabling it (government) to provide the citizens with such welfare goods and services. According to Margaret and Chris

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(2009), taxes and tax systems are fundamental components of any attempt to build nations and this is particularly the case in developing nations. Taxes underwrite the capacity of states to carry out their goals: they form one of the central arenas for the conducts of the state-society relations and they shape the balance between accentuation and redistribution that gives states their social characters. In summary, taxes build capacity, legitimacy and consent. The key components of any tax system are tax policies and tax administration. No tax is better than its policies. An essential objective of tax policies is to ensure the maximum possible compliance by taxpayers of all types with their taxation obligation. Unfortunately, in many developing countries, tax policies are usually weak and characterized by extensive abuse, corruption and coercion (Anyaduba, Eragbhe & Modugu, 2012).

Statement of the Problem

Low tax compliance is a matter of serious concern in many developing countries. This is because it limits the capacity of government to raise revenue for developmental purposes (Torgler, 2003). In Nigeria, tax administration is confronted with complex and thoughtful multidimensional problems. Ola (2001) maintained that revenue collected from income tax of individuals and corporate bodies are tend to be too low because of inadequate level of knowledge (tax literacy), poor association between tax authorities and taxpayers , insufficient number of quality and competent accountant among staff of tax authorities,

untrained and unqualified tax personnel lack skills on how to reach information or other technical procedures on how to utilize information available for the assessment and calculating tax in a best suitable manner (Ayodeji,2014). Frequently, the problems of tax administration and collection as identified by different findings are similar and tend to be unique. This is because the nature of the issue and the consequences are all same.

Soyole & Kajola (2006) noted that the problem of low revenue realization is negatively impacting on government expenditure. Furthermore, misuse of tax collected, bribery and corruption, incompetent tax personnel and poor accounting record-all these increase non-compliance attitudes and facilitate low tax return to the government. The situation led to the act of tax evasion as well as avoidance. Determining which regulatory enforcement strategy that will be most effective in gaining long-term voluntary compliance from taxpayers is a challenge for all tax authorities around the world (Kristir, 2008). A long-standing debate in the regulatory literature has been between those who think that individuals will comply with rules and regulations only when confronted with harsh sanctions and penalties, and those who believe that gentle persuasion and cooperation works in securing compliance (Ayres & Braithwaite, 1992).

In Nigeria enforcement of tax by the relevant tax authorities through the laid down procedures are always faced with problems. There has always

Essiet Victor Eniema

been arbitrary use of powers as well as abuses of procedures of enforcement of tax by the relevant tax authorities. This can be seen on how the taxpayer's property, non-refund of the balance of proceeds of sale, without due regard and compliance with the set-out conditions of doing that (Musa, 2014). Musa (2014) also maintained that the judicial arm of government is also not helping the effective enforcement of income tax, as there is the problem of delay in litigating tax matters due to long court processes which discourages taxing authority from taking litigation as an option for enforcing income tax in Nigeria.

In view of those highlighted problems, relevant tax authorities in Nigerian States are confronted with various challenges while considering the appropriate tax enforcement measures and therefore, lack the knowledge of the impact and effectiveness of tax enforcement strategy in achieving their objectives of adequately generating and optimizing tax revenue. Based on this, this study seeks to ascertain the impact of tax enforcement measures on revenue optimization in Nigerian States Internal Revenue Service and also highlight the appropriate tax enforcement measures to enhance revenue optimization in the States.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study is to determine the effect of the tax enforcement measures on revenue optimization in States' Internal Revenue Service in Nigeria. The study's specific objectives are to:

1. Determine the relationship between litigation and personal income tax in Nigerian States.
2. Ascertain the relationship between litigation and capital gain tax in Nigerian States.
3. Determine the relationship between powers of distraint and personal income tax in Nigerian States.
4. Ascertain the relationship between powers of distraint and capital gains tax in Nigerian States.
5. Ascertain the relationship between search and seizure and personal income tax in Nigerian States.
6. Determine the relationship between search and seizure and capital gain tax in Nigerian States.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Theoretical Review

A theoretical framework is an edge of reference that forms the foundation for observations, meanings of ideas, research plans, presentation, and analysis (LoBiondo & Haber, 2011). The study is anchored on the Ability to pay theory.

Ability to Pay Theory

Ability-to-pay or faculty theory was espoused by Adam Smith in the year 1776. The most popular and commonly accepted principle of equity or justice in taxation is that citizens of a country should pay taxes to the government in accordance with their ability to pay. It appears very reasonable and just that taxes should be levied on the basis of the taxable capacity of an individual. For instance, if the taxable capacity of

a person A is greater than the person B, the former should be asked to pay more taxes than the latter. It seems that if the taxes are levied on this principle as stated above, then justice can be achieved. But our difficulties do not end here. The fact is that when we put this theory in practice, our difficulties actually begin. The trouble arises with the definition of ability to pay. The economists are not unanimous as to what should be the exact measure of a person's ability or faculty to pay. The main viewpoints advanced in this connection are as follow:

Ownership of Property: Some economists are of the opinion that ownership of the property is a very good basis of measuring one's ability to pay. This idea is outrightly rejected on the ground that if a person earns a large income but does not spend on buying any property, he will then escape taxation. On the other hand, another person earning income buys property; he will be subjected to taxation. Is this not absurd and unjustifiable that a person, earning large income is exempted from taxes and another person with small income is taxed?

Tax on the Basis of Expenditure: It is also asserted by some economists that the ability or faculty to pay tax should be judged by the expenditure which a person incurs. The greater the expenditure, the higher should be the tax and vice versa. The viewpoint is unsound and unfair in every respect. A person having a large family to support has to spend more than a person having a small family. If we make expenditure as the test of one's ability to pay, the former person

who is already burdened with many dependents will have to' pay more taxes than the latter who has a small family. So this is unjustifiable.

Income as the Basics: Most of the economists are of the opinion that income should be the basis of measuring a man's ability to pay. It appears very just and fair that if the income of a person is greater than that of another, the former should be asked to pay more towards the support of the government than the latter. That is why in the modem tax system of the countries of the world, income has been accepted as the best test for measuring the ability to pay of a person.

Conceptual Review

Tax Enforcement Measures

Tax enforcement is a key issue in enhancing tax compliance. It involves compelling taxpayers to adhere or obey the provisions of the relevant tax laws. It is directed at taxpayers who fall short of their tax responsibilities. It includes levies, search & seizures, fines, seeking information from third parties, such as banks and court actions (Miguel & Lopez-Rodriguez, 2014). Enforcement is defined as the act of making sure that people obey a particular law or rule or the act of making sure that something happen or force somebody to do something. Enforcement is of two kinds; enforcement of tax laws and enforcement of judgment (Mohammed, 2015). Enforcement laws involves the use of application of all those relevant laws that will help and assist the tax official in the performance of his duties, laws not necessarily relating to the taxation but are relevant to the enforcement of tax laws.

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The various enforcement measures under the Nigerian Tax Act include litigation, exercise of search and seizure, exercise of power to lay distraint, denial of Tax Clearance Certificate, imposition of penalty and interest, authority to the Attorney-General of the federation (AGF) to deduct unremitted withholding tax from funds due to relevant agencies of government and authority to the Nigeria Customs Services (NCS) to refuse clearance to any defaulting shipping company (Arogundade, 2005). Enforcement must be convincing to tax payers to do the right thing. It is essential to note that the justification for legitimizing enforcement will be eroded if wrongly and harshly applied. Tanko (2015) stated that tax authority catches tax defaulters and cheats, increase level of compliance by enforcing relevant tax laws. While KPMG (2016) observed the aggressive tax enforcement procedures adopted by tax authorities in Nigeria, in recent times to enhance compliance to recover unpaid taxes from defaulting tax payers, enforcement compliance with tax provisions, defaulting companies has been sealed up. Hence, enforcement is the driving force that promotes tax compliance, and the inevitability of tax enforcement engenders self-assessment that can impact positively on revenue drive of the tax authority. The veritable plan of action available for administrators capable of enhancing revenue optimization is tax enforcement. Elleman and Obaro (2011) identified different types of tax enforcement procedures capable of inducing compliance as aggressive tax drive campaign by

relevant complying unit to meet non-complying companies to convince their decisions to effect tax payment, the use of judgment debts, sealing up of office premises and seizing movable properties of indebted taxpayers to compel him to pay the taxes due, the legitimate right to distraint the taxpayers of his goods, chattel real estate, financial instructions belonging to the indebted taxpayers for the purposes of sale to the tax amount due to government are possible enforcement procedures. Over the years, there has been a battle between the defaulting taxpayers and the relevant tax authorities in respect of enforcement of delinquent taxes. Taxpayers always seek to find ways or means to throw the burden of income taxation off their shoulders, thereby refusing to comply with the provisions of the relevant tax laws. There are set down procedures and standards that are to be followed by the tax officials that include, penalties, civil and criminal litigation, distraint of defaulting taxpayer's property, use of tax clearance certificate, etc. for effective enforcement of such delinquent taxes in the Nigeria tax laws (Musa, 2014). However, the researcher will only lay emphasis on; litigation, power to distraint and search & seizure. Tax enforcement is inevitable in the Nigerian tax system and administration; this is because of the ingenuity of the tax-payers in keeping what is due to the government or not paying their complete tax to the tax authority (Bariyama & Nwokah, 2009). Tax enforcement in Nigeria tax system has become one of the integral parts of

Essiet Victor Eniema

the tax administration given the ingenuity of taxpayers, individual and corporate bodies in keeping aside part of what is due to the government as taxes or not remitting same at all (Tanko, 2015).

Tax enforcement remains a desideratum and indeed inevitable in effort to improve revenue base in Nigeria. Tax law enforcement remains unavoidable in the tax system and administration in an effort to administer all the tax laws in Nigeria because it has the effect of punishing offenders by either distraintment or prosecution and act as deterrence for other members of the public while engendering voluntary compliance to the laws (Tanko, 2015). The application of tax monitoring and enforcement as administrative mechanism to achieve revenue optimization target is beneficial but must be applied with caution due to its adverse consequences. The essence of taxation is to benefit the citizens and not for punitive measures against the citizens, but tax enforcement involves persuasions, force and cohesion on taxpayers to extract outstanding tax liabilities owed to the government. Punitive measures are applied to tax defaulters for purposes of correcting behavior and improve tax compliance, close revenue optimization gap. James and Alloy (2004), contend that there is no doubt in the existence of sanction in tax administration. However, the extent they are needed and the enthusiasm of enforcement raised questions.

Litigation

It is a personal action which is instituted to compel payment or the doing of some other thing which is purely civil. It is a proceeding in a court of competent jurisdiction by one party against another for the forceful compliance or protection of a private right or for the redress or prevention of a private wrong. The civil action maybe involving a private party suing another private party or a private party suing or being sued by the government, but the proceedings do not involve criminal proceedings.

Under the Federal Inland Revenue Act civil actions are provided for under Section 34(1) and states as follows: "Without prejudice to any other provision of this Act, or any other Law listed in the first schedule to this Act, any amount due by way of Tax shall constitute a debt due to the service and maybe recovered by a civil action brought by the Service."

Civil litigation presupposes that the Federal Inland Revenue Service (hereinafter referred to as FIRS) has legally engaged the defaulting Taxpayer with all the statutory demand Notices, Reminders and distraint. Civil litigation is therefore undertaken as a last resort to redress a particular civil wrong perpetrated against the Service.

Criminal proceeding is defined as action or proceeding put in place or prosecuted by the state in its own name against a person(s) who is accused of an offense to discipline him therefore. A criminal proceeding is ordinarily one which if carried to an end may result in the imposition of

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a sentence such as death, imprisonment, fine or forfeiture of property. It is significant to acknowledge that the gamut of legal rules that rule the mechanism under which investigation, prosecution, adjudication and punishment of crime as well as protection of the Constitutional rights of the accused, constitutes a criminal procedure. Under the Federal Inland Revenue Act, offences and penalties are listed under Part VI of the Act.

Power of Distrain

To distrain means to seize and hold the property of a debtor to enforce payment of debts. The power to distrain is conferred on the FIRS under the provisions of section 33 of the Federal Inland Revenue Service Setup Act ("FIRSEA"). It is also contained in S.86 of the Companies Income Tax Act (CITA), S.104 of the Personal Income Tax Act (PITA), S.3(I)(b) of the Petroleum Profits Tax Act (PPTA). This power is exercised by a simple issuance of a warrant of distrain by the FIRS. To exercise the power to distrain, two conditions must be met. They are:

1. An assessment by the FIRS must be final and conclusive.
2. A demand notice must have been served and the time stipulated on the demand notice must have expired without the tax liability being settled.

Based on the statutory objection and appeal procedure, after the FIRS issues an assessment, the tax payer can send a notice of objection to the FIRS, within 30 days, who would either accept the objection or issue a notice of refusal to

amend. If the tax payer does not act in response to an assessment or does not challenge a notice of refusal to amend within 30 days, the assessment becomes final and conclusive. Upon the assessment becoming final and conclusive, a demand notice would then be issued for the liability. A demand notice can also be issued by way of judgment where a tax liability is determined by a court to be paid within a stipulated time.

Recently the FIRS started to enforce filing of tax returns and payment of taxes by distraining properties, and ensuring the arrest of principal officers of defaulting companies. This alternative means of tax forceful compliance is as a result of the need to generate revenue in the light of declining oil revenue. There is however a question as to whether this procedure follows due process? The Federal Inland Revenue Services ("FIRS") help by officers and men of the Nigerian Police Force has been raiding and distraining payers. In some cases, the Press is invited to witness the exercise leading to negative comments in the media. The raid could be as a result of tax payer failed to file tax returns but in most instances, it is caused in respect of failure to pay taxes for an extended period. A responsible officer of the defaulting company (usually the managing director and/or chief finance officer) is "arrested" by the police for questioning and asked to give an undertaking as to the settlement of the outstanding tax liabilities before being released.

Essiet Victor Eniema

Search and Seizure

This refers to the methods used by the relevant tax authorities where they are satisfied that there is reasonable grounds for suspecting that an offence involving any form of total or partial non-disclosure of information or any irregularity or an offence in connection with or in relation to tax has been committed and, is of the opinion that evidence of the offence or irregularity is to be found in the premises, the registered office or any other office or place of management of trade, vocation, profession or business or in the residence of principal officer, factor, agent or representative of the individuals, the relevant tax authority is authorized if necessary by force to conduct a search as such (Musa, 2014). This is provided under sections 53(1) of the PITA and section 64 of the CITA power to effect search and seizure has also been provided under sections 29, 30, 31 and 36 of the FIRS Act.

From the combined effect of the above sections, there must be a warrant and the occupier of the premises to be searched must be consented. A search must also be conducted by the same gender sections 36(4) of the ACT provides that “no person shall be bodily searched under this section except by person who is of the same gender as the person to be bodily searched”. Thus, where the provisions are breached, it can be the basis for an action for assault against the erring tax official. In the case of serious tax infraction or suspicion of tax abuses, the FIRS is authorized to carry out inspections, searches, seizures, made copy of evidence, obstruct or

break into premises etc. however, in the course of carrying out any of these activities, the FIRS ACT forbids the search of a person to be carried by a person of the opposite gender. In other words, a man can only be searched by another man and vice versa. This is an attempt to protect the culture and religious sensibilities of most Nigerians. Similar provisions with respect to search are contained in the penal code and criminal code applicable in Nigeria. But such an infraction will not affect the admissibility of any evidence so illegally obtained. Section 37 of the constitution provides the right to privacy. This has far reaching tax implications that will be analyzed. The provisions stipulate that “the privacy of citizens, their homes, correspondence, telephone conversations and telegraphic communications is hereby guaranteed and protected (Musa, 2014).

Revenue optimization

The term revenue has been defined by various authors in different ways. Adam (2006) defined revenue as the fund required by the government to finance its activities. These funds are generated from different sources such as taxes, borrowing, fine, fees etc. It is also defined as the total amount of income that accrues to an organization (public or private) within a specified period of time (Hamid, 2008). States revenue comprises of receipt from taxation as well as those which are not the proceeds of taxation, but of either the realization from the sale of government properties or other interests and returns from loans and investment earning.

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Bhatia (2001) contends that revenue receipt includes "routine" and "earned" income. For these reasons, according to him, revenue do not include borrowing and recovery of loans from other parties, but it includes tax receipts, donations, grants, fees and fines and so on. Similarly, Pearce (1986) defined government revenue as all the money received other than from issue of debt, and liquidation of investments. Government revenue includes tax collections, charges and miscellaneous revenues, utility and insurance trust revenue for all funds and agencies of a government. Public revenue according to Stephen and Osagie (1985) is concerned with various ways in which the government raises revenue. From the above definitions, it can be said that revenue is the total amount of income accruing to a state from various sources within a specified period of time. State government, like the other two tiers of government, has sources and uses of revenue. Osisami (1994) states that there are basically two types of revenue that accrues to state governments. These are internally generated revenue and revenue allocated from the Federation Account.

Internally generated revenue are those revenues that are derived within the state from various sources such as taxes (pay as you earn, direct assessment, capital gain taxes, etc), and motor vehicle license, among others. While the statutory allocation from Federation Account, Value Added Tax constitute the external source. Most states of the federation get the bulk of their

revenue in form of statutory allocation from the federation account to finance their expenditure programs. (Ibrahim, 2002; Ishaq, 2002, and Hamid, 2008). State Governments as the second tier of government in Nigeria derive its revenue from various sources. However, it should be noted that sources of revenue are by no means uniform among the states. States derive their revenue depending on the resources available to them (Adam, 2006). The share of federation account to states constitutes 57.97% in 2002 of the total revenue plus grant and this rose to 65.82% in 2006; while the internally generated revenue declined from 13.38% in 2002 to 8.11% in 2006 (CBN,2006). The average percentages of internally generated revenue in relation to the federal allocation were between 5-9 percent for most non-oil producing states in the recent past. Kano was able to slightly exceed 10% in 2004 to date due to aggressive revenue generation efforts, with Lagos state as the only exception. Recurrent expenditure according to Jimoh (2007) is the type of expenditure that happens repeatedly on daily, weekly or even monthly basis.

Empirical Review

Empirical literatures on tax enforcement are limited and most of the studies were foreign, for instance, Antonio, Carlo and Eliana (2013) examined the effect of tax enforcement on tax morale. The data used in this study were sourced from the bank of Italy in the survey of household income and wealth (SHIW). These data are the main source of information for the analysis of

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income distribution and socio-economic trends in Italy as they provide a representative sample of the population of Italian household since the end of the 1970s. Starting from the late 1980s it is characterized by a bi-annual frequency and a sample size of about 8000 households. By using a unique data-set that merges a representative sample of Italian households with administrative data on tax enforcement. Firstly, the study found that tax morale is positively correlated with tax enforcement. Secondly, to deal with possible endogeneity of tax enforcement, this study showed that result is confirmed in an IV specification using the change in the tax gap at the provincial level as an instrument for tax enforcement. Finally, the study provides evidence that the impact of tax enforcement and social environment is stronger at low quartile of tax morale. The result showed that beside that of lowering the expected value of tax compliance through its effect on tax morale.

Miguel and Lopez-Rodriguez (2014) ascertained the heterogeneous responses to effective tax enforcement using evidence from Spanish Firms. This paper investigates the effect of monitoring the information trail generated by firms' activities in order to improve tax compliance. The study used quasi-experimental variation provided by a large Taxpayers Unit (LTU) in Spain to empirically test the theoretical prediction on firms' responses to an increase in monitoring effort. Firms with more than \$6million in reported revenue are monitored by the LTU; which devotes more resources to

verifying the transaction reported by those firms. Using financial statement from practically the entire universe of Spanish firms for the period 1999-2007, the study finds substantial bunching of firms just below the LTU threshold. On average, the study estimated that bunches reduce their reported revenue \$101000(1.7% total revenue) to avoid falling in the high enforcement regime. Adjustment for resource costs of evasion faced by firms, the study estimate that the marginal butchering firm reduces its reported revenue by up to \$593000 (9.9%). The response is weak in sector where most sales are made to final consumers, retail, and restaurants) and strong in sectors where firms sell intermediate goods to other businesses wholesale, manufacturing). This result suggests that monitoring effort by the tax authorities had the traceability of the information reported by the firms are complements, and both are necessary for effective tax enforcement. Finally, we provide suggestive evidence that firm under their monitoring effort also misreport their material and labor expenditures to evade taxes, even in the presence of third party reporting.

Williams (2002) analyzed tax return data from 528 taxpayers who had previously been prosecuted for failing to lodge their tax returns with the Australian Taxation Office (ATO). His results showed that prosecutions were successful in obtaining subsequent lodgment compliance, but he qualified this by showing that lodgment rates reduced significantly, in subsequent years

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once the initial threat of deterrence had subsided.

In another study that drew on survey data from 477 Australian university graduates, Mohamed and Braithwaite (2005) found that the significant relationship between feelings of shame and compliance was mediated by participants' feelings of being “dissociated” from tax system where dissociation seemed to reflect disregard for the legitimacy of tax law.

Murphy and Harris (2007) analyzed survey data from a group of 652 tax offenders. The taxpayers were asked about their enforcement experience with the tax office. Those who perceived their enforcement to be stigmatizing in nature were in turn more likely to display anger towards the tax office, and were less likely to express feelings of remorse for their wrong- doing. These emotional reactions in turn were found to mediate the effect of stigmatization on subsequent tax compliance behavior; in other words, those displaying hostility towards their enforcement experience were more likely to report having evaded their taxes two years later.

Kristina (2008) carried out research on the topic” Enforcing Tax Compliance: To punish or persuade?” Its main aim is to assess whether deterrence or an accommodative-based approach to enforcement is more effective in increasing support for the law' and lowering the rate of tax offenders. The study will do this by examining the survey responses of 652 tax offenders who have been through a serious enforcement experience with the Australian

Taxation Office (ATO). The study specifically seeks to replicate and extend those findings which suggest that stigmatizing versus reiterative forms of disapproval is relevant to predicting offence in the context of taxation. Second, it seeks to test whether feelings of resentment towards the law and authority mediate the effect of disapproval on offending behavior. The study showed that depending on how an enforcement experience is perceived by offenders (as either stigmatic or reiterative in nature) can influence the feelings of resentment they experience, but more importantly these feelings of resentment mediate the effect of punishment on subsequent compliance behavior. In other words, it is these feelings of resentment in response to disapproval that go on to predict who will and will not comply with their subsequent obligations under the law.

Henrik, Martin, Claus, Soren and Emmanuel (2008) carried out an experimental evaluation of tax evasion and tax enforcement in Denmark. This paper analyzes a randomized evaluation of tax enforcement and tax evasion carried out in collaboration with Danish Inland Revenue (SKAT). In the base year, a stratified and representative sample of over 40,000 Danish individual tax filers was selected for the experiment. Half of those tax filers were randomly selected to be thoroughly audited, while the rest were deliberately not audited. The following fear “threat-of-audited” letters were randomly assigned and sent to those tax filers. This experiment allowed them to study income

Essiet Victor Eniema

tax compliance in Denmark in great detail, as well as the causal effects of (a) prior audits and (b) audit probability on subsequent reporting behavior. The study finds that tax compliance in Denmark is high overall, but that there is substantial tax evasion on purely self-reported income, i.e. income which is not subject to double reporting by third parties. This suggests that the informational framework is more important than social or psychological effects in explaining tax compliance. The study also finds that threat-of-audit letters have significant effects on self-reported income adjustments, and that these effects are larger for tax filers not audited in the previous year. Letters also increase the likelihood of downward adjustment (which reduced tax liability), which can be explained by tax payers trading of the cost of filing correctly against the cost of having to deal with tax examiners. Prior audits also significantly increase the likelihood of self-reporting higher incomes the following year, implying that individuals update their beliefs about audit probability based on experiencing an audit.

METHODOLOGY

The research design adopted for this study is survey design. The reason is that the entire population cannot be studied and a survey is considered appropriate. The population for this study shall be all the taxpayers and States Internal Revenue Service (SIRS) in six (6)

selected States with at least one in each of the six geopolitical zone in Nigeria, namely: Akwa Ibom State (South South), Enugu State (South East), Osun State (South West), Nasarawa State (North Central), Bauchi State (North East) and Kaduna State (North West). Following how large the target population is, the sample size for the study was divided into two (individual taxpayers and relevant tax authority). A total of 300 individual taxpayers will be interviewed in the six (6) States (50 per state) while 300 sets of questionnaire will be physically administered on the State Internal Revenue Service in the six (6) States (50 per state) cutting across at least a branch in 5 local government in each State. Conclusively, the total sample size was 600 respondents evenly distributed across the six geopolitical zones in Nigeria. The principal method of data collection adopted in this study was questionnaire, interviews and observations. Each of the Study States were allocated one hundred (100) sets of questionnaire (50 for individuals and 50 for SIRS). The demographic data was analyzed using frequency tables depicting percentages and frequency distributions for the sample characteristics. The univariate analysis of each variable was done using mean scores, standard deviation. While the bivariate analysis was carried out using the Pearson product moment correlation coefficient with the aid of statistical package for social sciences.

DATA ANALYSIS

Relationship between Litigation and Personal Income Tax

Table 1: Correlation Result for litigation and personal income tax

		Litigation	PIT
Litigation	Pearson Correlation	1	.929**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	581	581
PIT	Pearson Correlation	.929**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	581	581

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS Output Version 21.0

Table 1 illustrates the test for the first previously postulated bivariate hypothetical statement. The results showed that:

Ho1: There is no significant relationship between litigation and personal income tax (r = 0.929, p = 0.000 < 0.05);

Based on the result illustrated, the previous bivariate null hypothetical statement is hereby rejected as the study finds that: there is a significant relationship between litigation and personal income tax.

Relationship between Litigation and Capital Gains Tax

Table 2: Correlation Result for Litigation and Capital Gains Tax

		Litigation	CGT
Litigation	Pearson Correlation	1	.933**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	581	581
CGT	Pearson Correlation	.933**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	581	581

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS Output Version 21.0

Table 2 illustrates the test for the second previously postulated bivariate hypothetical statement. The results showed that:

Ho2: There is no significant relationship between litigation and capital gains tax (r = 0.933, p = 0.000 < 0.05).

Based on the results illustrated, the previous second bivariate null hypothetical statement is hereby rejected as the study finds that: There is a

significant relationship between litigation and capital gain tax.

Relationship between Power of Distrain and Personal Income Tax

Table 3: Correlation Result for power of distrain and personal income tax

		Power Distrain	ofPIT
Power of Distrain	Pearson Correlation	1	.936**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	581	581
PIT	Pearson Correlation	.936**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	581	581

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS Output Version 21.0

Table 3 illustrates the test for the third previously postulated bivariate hypothetical statement. The results show that:

H₀₃: There is no significant relationship between power of distrain and personal income tax (r = 0.936, p = 0.000 < 0.05).

Based on the results illustrated, the previous third bivariate null hypothetical statement is hereby rejected as the study finds that: There is a significant relationship between power of distrain and personal income tax.

Relationship between Power of Distrain and Capital Gains Tax

Table 4: Correlation Result for Power of Distrain and Capital Gains Tax

		Power Distrain	of CGT
Power of Distrain	Pearson Correlation	1	.945**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	581	581
CGT	Pearson Correlation	.945**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	581	581

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS Output Version 21.0

Table 4 illustrates the test for the fourth previously postulated bivariate hypothetical statement. The results showed that:

HO₄: There is no significant relationship between power of distraint and capital gains tax (r = 0.945, p = 0.000 < 0.05).

Based on the results illustrated, the previous fourth bivariate null hypothetical statement is

hereby rejected as the study finds that: There is a significant relationship between power of distraint and capital gains tax.

Relationship between Search and Seizure and Personal Income Tax

Table 5: Correlation Result for Search and Seizure and Personal Income Tax

		Search & Seizure PIT	
Search and seizure	Pearson Correlation	1	.868**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	581	581
PIT	Pearson Correlation	.868**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	581	581

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS Output Version 21.0

Table 5 illustrates the test for the fifth previously postulated bivariate hypothetical statement. The results showed that:

HO₅: There is no significant relationship between search and seizure and personal income tax (r = 0.868, p = 0.000 < 0.05).

Based on the results illustrated, the previous fifth bivariate null hypothetical statement is hereby rejected as the study finds that: There is a significant relationship between search and seizure and personal income tax.

Relationship between Search and Seizure and Capital Gains Tax

Table 6 Correlation Result for Search and Seizure and capital gains Tax

		Search & Seizure CGT	
Search and seizure	Pearson Correlation	1	.914**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	581	581
CGT	Pearson Correlation	.914**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	581	581

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** Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS Output Version 21.0

Table 6 illustrates the test for the sixth previously postulated bivariate hypothetical statement. The results show that for:

H₀₆: There is no significant relationship between search and seizure and capital gain tax ($r = 0.914, p = 0.000 < 0.05$).

Based on the results illustrated, the previous sixth bivariate null hypothetical statement is hereby rejected as the study finds that: There is a significant relationship between search and seizure and capital gain tax.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Based on the analyses and findings above, the researcher thus concludes that Litigation significantly influences the personal income tax; Litigation influences capital gains tax; Power of Distrain significantly influences personal income tax; Power of Distrain significantly influences capital gains tax; Search and seizure significantly influences personal income tax; Search and seizure significantly influences capital gains tax. Based on the findings and conclusions of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Litigation support should be adopted by State internal Revenue Service in Nigeria as it will enhance the payment of tax by the tax payers.

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2. Tax penalty should be stiff enough to serve as deterrent to would-be tax defaulters; also, power of distraint should be encouraged.

3. Search and Seizure is appropriate when a crime is suspected and therefore will enhance revenue optimization if adopted.

4. Judicious use of taxpayer's money should be made and be seen to have been properly utilized. This will encourage taxpayers to continue to pay taxes.

5. The tax authorities should organize seminars, workshop and trainings of taxpayers periodically on tax enforcement measures. This will encourage self-compliance.

6. Tax education is recommended to further enlighten people about the need to fulfill tax obligations even right from the schools.

Contribution to Knowledge

The issue of tax enforcement measures and revenue optimization positively impacts revenue base through personal income tax and capital gains tax in Nigerian States. Again, litigation, power of distraint, search and seizure strongly influence the revenue optimization from Capital Gains tax as indicated by the findings. Therefore, the main contribution of this study to knowledge is that tax enforcement measures' proxy of litigation, power of distraint, search and seizure as identified in the research gap significantly influences on revenue optimization of State Internal Revenue Services.

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